

A REVIEW ON “TRANSUNGUAL DRUG DELIVERY: A PROMISING ROUTE TO TREAT NAIL DISORDERS”

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this review is to explore the difficulties in penetration of drug across nail plate & enhancement of bioavailability of antifungal drug. Nail drug delivery systems face significant challenges due to the nail plate's inherent barrier properties, hindering effective treatment of conditions like onychomycosis and psoriasis. Conventional topical treatments often yield unsatisfactory results, emphasizing the need for innovative strategies to enhance drug penetration. This review explores recent advancements in nail drug delivery, including chemical method such as Keratolytic enhancers, physical method techniques such as microneedles and Laser ultraviolet light, mechanical method such as nail avulsion, Nail abrasion and novel drug formulations like nail lacquers and nanoparticles. By overcoming the challenges of nail drug delivery, these innovations hold promise for improving

treatment efficacy and patient outcomes, ultimately enhancing the management of nail disorders. This systemic review covers the anatomy of a human nail, diseases related to nail plate, the formulations designed for nail application and some techniques used to enhance the topical bioavailability of the drugs across the nail, latest trends in drug delivery across the nail.

1] INTRODUCTION

One kind of medication administration method is the transungual drug delivery system. "Ungual" means "the nail," and "trans" means "through." Specifically, the transungual drug delivery technique involves administering a medication through the nail, which transfers the

medication through the nail and exhibits a specific impact on the diseased nail portion. the nail plates that allow drugs to pass through them.^[1] The most visible part of the nail apparatus is nail plate. It consists of tightly packed dead cells and is highly keratinized. These plates might be tiny, huge, broad, narrow, hard, smooth, ridged, thin, etc.^[3] The dorsal and intermediate layers of the human nail plate are formed from the matrix, whereas the ventral layer is derived from the nail bed. The soft keratin makes up the intermediate layer, which is three-quarters of the nail's thickness. Only a few cell layers thick, the dorsal top layer is made of strong keratin and contains a comparatively large amount of sulfur, mostly in the form of the amino acid cysteine, which makes up 94% of the nail's weight. The nail plate is mostly where the top layer of the nail diffuses. Numerous pathological alterations take place in the soft hyponychial layer that makes up the ventral layer. Therefore, an efficient medication concentration in the ventral nail plate would be crucial for the treatment of various nail disorders.^[6] The drug's penetration is controlled by the nail plate.^[2] However, only a few number of drugs may penetrate the nail to provide the intended effects due to its extremely strong structure. Thus, topical drug administration is more efficient than oral drug delivery and has less negative effects on the body or the nail region.^[1] Disorders of the nail unit can vary from relatively harmless disorders like pigmentation in heavy smokers to severe and life-threatening ones including infection, inflammation, dystrophied, or hypertrophied nail units. These illnesses have an impact on patients' physical, social, and psychological well-being, and they can significantly lower their quality of life. Topical treatment is constrained by the poor permeability of the nail plates, whereas oral medication has systemic side effects and drug interactions.^[4,5] This study aims to investigate the challenges associated with medication penetration through the nail plate and the improvement of antifungal drug bioavailability. To treat not only topical nail illnesses but also to take into account the potential to reach systemic circulation and nearby target areas.^[7] Iontophoresis, acid etching, carbon dioxide laser, hydration and occlusion, electroporation, UV light, photodynamic therapy, sonophoresis, and phonophoresis are physical techniques for improving penetration. Chemicals such as sulphites, mercaptans, hydrogen peroxides, urea, water, keratolytic agents, keratinolytic enzymes, etc., increase the drug's penetration potential. Additionally, nail abrasion and nail avulsion mechanically improve penetration.^[1]

Fig. 1. Nail Structure.

2] NAIL ANATOMY & STRUCTURE

The nail is a complex unit composed of five major modified cutaneous structures: the nail matrix, nail plate, nail bed, cuticle (eponychium), and nail folds.

Fig: 2 a) Outer Structure Of Human Nail.

Fig :2 b) Inner Structure Of Human Nail.

The human nail's structure consists of

2.1. Matrix (matrix unguis, keratogenous membrane, nail matrix, onychostroma)

The nail matrix is situated far from the nail plate and proximal nail fold. About midway between the proximal nail fold and the distal interphalangeal joint, the proximal nail matrix starts. The lunula, a white half-moon structure, is the distal nail matrix that is visible through the nail plate. The only component of the nail unit that contains melanocytes is the nail matrix, which is also in charge of creating the hard nail plate. The nail plate is created by pushing the onychocytes, or nail cells, superficially and distally. Sections of the nail plate are

formed by various components of the nail matrix. Typically, the proximal nail matrix forms the dorsal portion of the nail plate, whereas the distal nail matrix forms the ventral aspect. Nonetheless, the proximal nail matrix makes up 80% of the nail plate. As a result, the nail plate will sustain little harm from a biopsy or operation of the distal nail matrix.^[8]

2.2. Nail bed

The nail bed starts distal to the lunula and ends at the hyponychium. It is connected to the ventral surface of the nail plate. Longitudinal epidermal ridges hold the nail plate to the nail bed. By increasing the surface area of the nail plate's connection to the underlying nail bed, these ridges on the ventral nail plate surface complement those on the nail bed and improve the adhesion between the two surfaces. If the keratins required for the creation of this layer of the epidermis are absent, the nail bed does not create a stratum corneum. The nail bed loses the longitudinal ridges and starts to express the keratins required to form the stratum corneum, though, if onycholysis or loss of the nail plate takes place. A thin layer of the collagenous dermis lies under the nail bed and is attached to the periosteum of the distal phalanx below. In the context of nail infection, the absence of subcutaneous fat may raise the risk of distal phalanx osteomyelitis.^[8]

2.3. Nail sinus (*sinus unguis*)

It is the deep groove that the nail root is placed in.^[9]

2.4. Nail root (*radix unguis*)

It is the portion of the nail that is implanted beneath the skin, or the nail base, in the nail sinus.^[9] It comes from the tissue underneath the matrix that is actively developing.^[10]

2.5. Nail plate (*corpus unguis*)

The transparent keratin protein, which is composed of amino acids, is the real nail. It creates a robust, flexible substance in the nail from many layers of flattened, dead cells.^[10] The capillaries underneath give the plate its pink appearance.^[11] The shape of the underlying bone determines its transverse shape.^[10]

2.6. The Distal edge

Other names for it include anterior margin, *margo liber*, and free edge. It is the nail's margin that extends from the nail or the area that is not in contact with the skin. The layer of epithelial cells under the nail plate and at the distal end is called the hyponychium, or "quick."^[13]

The hyponychium serves as the nail bed's protective covering.^[14]

2.7. Onchodermal band

In some peoples, the greyish coloured layer is seen known as onchodermal band. This band is present in all the peoples but in some cases it can be easily seen by naked eyes. The onchodermal band is present in between the hyponychium and the nail plate.^[15]

2.8. The Nail root

It is the last nail segment found in the nail sinus. It is sometimes referred to as the germinal matrix or radix sinus. The matrix tissues are what give it its shape. This portion extends for a few millimeters in the nail. It creates the nail's greatest mass.^[16]

2.9. The Nail wall

The cutaneous membrane fold that covers the nail's root and both sides is known as the nail wall. The nail wall is known scientifically as "valum unguis." The "lateral margin" or "margo lateralis" is the margin that is visible on both sides of the nail and beneath the nail wall.^[17]

2.10. The Hyponychium

It is an additional nail component that creates the connection between the fingertip's skin and free edge. In order to shield the nail against infection by any kind of microbe, hypochonychium forms a covering over the nail. Making nails resistant to water is the other purpose.^[17]

2.11. The Eponychium

Additional names for the eponychium include "cuticle" and "proximal fold." The proximal fold is located near the epinychium's terminal. The freshly developed nail bed is protected by the proximal fold. This layer, which is nearly invisible skin, is composed of dead cells.^[19] From the nail wall to the nail root, it is the layer of epithelial cells.^[18] While the epithelium is made of live cells and contacting it can result in any nail issue, the cuticle is made of a covering of dead cells that may be removed during a manicure.^[19] The eponychium border that encloses the lunula's strip is called the perionix.^[18]

2.12. The Paronychium

It is the covering of soft tissues that envelops the whole nail. Paronychia is the term for the infection of this region. The nail's paronychium, which is made of an epidemic layer, borders it.^[20]

2.13. lateral margin : (margo lateralis)

It is located on the sides of the nail beneath the nail wall, and the lateral borders are imbedded in the cutaneous slits known as the nail groove or fold (sulcus matricis unguis).^[16]

3] GROWTH OF NAIL

In animals, the length of the finger's last phalanges determines how quickly the nail grows. The nail grows more quickly on the index finger than the little finger because the index finger's phalanges are longer than those of the little finger. In humans, the fingernails on the hands grow more quickly than those on the legs.^[21] The nail's developing portion is found under the epidermis, which is the layer under the skin. The nail's epidermis is its only living component. The typical monthly growth rate of a human finger nail is around 4-5 mm (0.20 in), whereas the average monthly growth rate of a toenail is approximately 2-3 mm (0.08 in).^[22] Some researchers say that the nails grow after death but the reason behind this is when the death of a person occurs the skin present around the nail is getting continuously shrinking due to the dehydration process, hence it looks like the nails are growing. As this is a slow process, it took much more time.^[23]

4] PERMEABILITY

The highly complex structure of keratinized tissues makes up the nail. As a result, researchers believed that nails were impermeable to all substances, however, this isn't entirely accurate. Some medications can pass through the nails, demonstrating their impact on nail medications. The nails are more permeable than the skin, which is a curious fact. Drug entry into nail diseases is significantly enhanced by this permeability. Toxic chemicals, however, can also penetrate the nail and pose a risk to the nail. Since water readily permeates nails, pharmaceutically active ingredients are manufactured as base water to treat nail ailments. The active components include sodium hypochlorite, natamycin, miconazole, and salicylic acid.^[24]

5] FUNCTION OF NAILS IN HUMAN BODY

The primary purpose of nails is to help hold objects by hand, a process known as "extended precision function grip."^[27] Nails also serve as a useful tool for cutting, scraping, or pinching very small particles. In addition to protecting the delicate tips of finger and toe nails from external injuries, they also exert opposite pressure or counter pressure on the fingertip, facilitating tip movement and touch sensation.^[26]

6] EFFECT OF DIFFERENT NUTRIENTS ON NAILS

6.1. Vitamin A

A vital micronutrient is vitamin A. The vitamin has an impact on our body's several organs, including the immune system, eyes, and reproduction. Nail brittleness, dryness, and increased instability can result from a vitamin A deficiency.^[24]

6.2. Calcium and Vitamin D

The fact that vitamins and calcium function in conjunction indicates that they are interconnected. They detect muscle contraction, support the body's homeostatic processes, aid in the coagulation process, and facilitate impulse transmission across nerve cells.^[24]

6.3. Vitamin B12

Dark nails and dry nails might result from a vitamin B12 deficiency. The form of nails is altered by low vitamin B12 levels, resulting in ridges and rounded or curled nails.^[24]

6.4. Proteins

The proteins are the building blocks of our body therefore insufficient dietary protein can cause the reduce Haemoglobin level in body and due to reduced Haemoglobin level the oxygen carrying capacity of blood decreases and body suffers with anemia like condition. Resulting to this below the nails the white patches are begin to seen. In iron deficiency anemia like condition the colour of nails become pale yellow and they become fragile and shape of nails become convex.^[25]

6.5. Fatty Acids

Only the necessary fatty acids are crucial for the maintenance of good skin and nails; not all fatty acids are involved in the metabolism of skin and nails. Nail splitting or flattening may result from a fatty acid (linoleic acid) deficit.^[25]

7] NAIL DISORDERS

A] Onychomycosis (Tinea unguium)

Onychomycosis is a fungal infection of the nail, causing discoloration and thickening of the affected nail plate, and is the most common nail infection worldwide. Microscopy and fungal culture are the gold standard techniques for onychomycosis diagnosis. There are several treatment options available, including oral antifungals, topicals and devices. Oral antifungals have higher cure rates and shorter treatment periods than topical treatments, but have adverse

side effects such as hepatotoxicity and drug interactions. Terbinafine, itraconazole and fluconazole are most commonly used, with new oral antifungals such as fosravuconazole being evaluated. Topical treatments, such as efinaconazole, tavaborole, ciclopirox and amorolfine have less serious side effects.^[28]

➤ **Onychomycosis Classified into four distinct class**

- 1) **Distal subungual onychomycosis**- This kind of onychomycosis is the most prevalent, and the bacteria *Trichophyton rubrum*, which lives in the gap between the nail plate and nail bed, is the causal agent.^[29]
- 2) **superficial onychomycosis (WSO)**- The formation of fungi in the nail plate which produces the "white patches" appearance. White spots can also occasionally be caused by a protein shortage. Therefore, a laboratory test is performed for diagnosis.^[30]
- 3) **Proximal subungual onychomycosis** - Although it is not more common, immunosuppressed individuals may experience it. Here, the fungus infiltrates the recently developed nail plate.^[29]
- 4) **Candidal onychomycosis**- The microbe of the genus *Candida* is responsible for all of this. Constant nail contact with water might result in this kind of onychomycosis.^[31]

FIG. 3: ONYCHOMYCOSIS (FUNGAL INFECTION).

B] Green nail syndrome

The infection known as "green nails" or chloronychia is mostly brought on by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, however it can also be brought on by other bacterial or fungal infections. The classic combination of clinical appearances includes disto-lateral onycholysis, proximal

chronic paronychia, and green staining of the nail plate.^[32] People whose nails are constantly in contact with moisture or water are more vulnerable to this disease; if someone has artificial nail coating on their nails, the infection may also cause a separation between the natural nail bed and the artificial nail coating. If the infection is not treated promptly, it may cause the separation of the nail plate from the nail bed.^[33] Quinolone (Ciprofloxacin) is an oral medication that can be used to treat this condition. Silver Sulfadiazine, Gentamicin, Nadifloxacin, and Ciprofloxacin are the medications that can be used topically. Certain antibiotics, such as Bacitracin and Polymyxin B, can also be used to treat green nails.^[34]

Fig. 4: Pseudomonas bacterial infection.

C] Leukonychia

This is the most frequent kind of nail damage between the nail plate and nail bed, when a white line or spot emerges on one or more nails. The spot may be caused by an air bubble caught between the nail bed and nail late as a result of stress. The words leuko indicate “white” and onych indicate "nails," respectively.

➤ Leukonychia Classified into five distinct class

- 1) Leukonychia totalis:** As the name suggests, the entire nail turns white in this situation. The primary cause of this illness is hypoalbuminemia, or low blood albumin levels. Protein dysfunction, liver failure, and kidney failure are the causes of hypoalbuminemia. This is a hereditary illness that can also be brought on by a patient's hypersensitivity to medications in the sulphonamide family.^[35]

- 2) **Leukonychia partialis:** As the name suggests, a portion of the nail turns white with this illness. Leukonychia totalis develops if partial leukonychia is not treated at a certain period.^[35]
- 3) **Leukonychia striata:** Mees-lines leukonychia and transverse leukonychia are other names for this disease. This disorder causes the nail to become white parallel to the lunula, or nail base. This is generally brought on by physical damage to the nail or infection of the nail matrix. This illness is brought on by heavy metals like lead, arsenic poisoning, or excessive manicures.^[36,37]
- 4) **Leukonychia punctata:** This kind of leukonychia, which affects young children and nail bitters, is the most prevalent. It was brought on by trauma as well as air becoming trapped between the nail plate and nail bed.^[38]
- 5) **Longitudinal leukonychia:** It is a rare illness that is hardly observed in any patient. An approximately 1-1.5 cm white line emerges on the nail in this case. Every nutritional level in the body is examined, and the appropriate supplement is administered, in order to cure any kind of leukonychia.^[35]

Fig. 5: Leukonychia (Milky Spot).

D] Paronychia Infection

A bacterial or fungal infection of the hand or toe nails is called paronychia. The infection happens along the sides of the nails, where the skin and nails meet.

➤ **Paronychia Classified into two distinct class**

- 1) **Acute Paronychia:** This type of infection are last for short time. Staphylococcus aureus and Candida albicans are the germs that cause this kind of paronychia.^[39] Localized discomfort, redness, and swelling are the first signs of an infection. The duration of the infection is six weeks. Trauma, thorn injuries, nail biting, finger sucking, etc., can all result

in infection. antimicrobial therapy for medications such as amoxicillin-clavulanate potassium (Augmentin) and clindamycin (Cleocin).^[40]

- 2) **Chronic Paronychia:** This kind of infection develops gradually and lasts a long time. This was mostly brought on by the nails' constant interaction with moisture. The cuticle splits from the nail plate in this illness, making the nail plate more vulnerable to infection. The drug treatment includes combination of penicillin with cephalosporin and aminoglycosides, Acyclovir and Valacyclovir.^[41]

Fig. 6: Paronychia Infection.

E] Onychauxis

Onychauxis is a prevalent nail condition, especially in older and disabled people. The hypertrophic nail plate turns out to be unpleasant and ugly. We examine nonsurgical treatments that are intended to relieve symptoms and surgical choices that are meant to give permanent repair.^[42]

Fig.7: Onychauxis.

F] Onychatrophia

The nail plate atrophy or drying away acts as what causes them to be less shiny, smaller, and occasionally lose all together. This abnormality may be caused by illness or injury.^[43]

Fig.8: Onychatrophia.

G] Onychogrypos

Sometimes they are the consequence of trauma and are characterized by a thicker nail plate. This kind of nail plate will bend inward, compressing the nail bed. In order to ease the discomfort, surgery may be necessary.^[44]

Fig.9: Onychogrypos.

H] Onychorrhex

Brittle nails that frequently peel, break vertically, or have vertical ridges. Heredity or the usage of strong solvents at work or at home, such as cleaning products, may be the cause of this abnormality. To rule out illness, one may want to consult a doctor even though oil or paraffin treatments can rehydrate the nail plate.^[44]

Fig.10: Onychorrhex.

I] Beaus lines

Characterized by linear depressions and horizontal lines of darker cells. The issue results from any disruption in the nail plate's protein creation and can be brought on by trauma, disease, dehydration, any serious metabolic condition, chemotherapy, or any harmful event.^[44]

Fig.10: Beaus lines.

J] Koilonychia

Most frequently brought on by deficiencies in iron anemia. These nails are thin and concave, with elevated ridges.^[44]

Fig.11: Koilonychia.

8. DIAGNOSIS

The differential diagnosis can be narrowed with the use of a thorough history and physical examination, but a diagnosis made without laboratory confirmation is extremely erroneous. Onychomycosis and a number of nail disorders have similar clinical presentations.^[45,46]

A rapid, non-invasive, and very useful diagnostic method for distinguishing onychomycosis from other nail conditions is dermoscopy.^[47] Common characteristics observed during dermoscopy are longitudinal streaks and sharp, spiked proximal boundaries.^[48,49] In order to distinguish between acute and chronic diseases, paronychia is diagnosed by a clinical examination and history. The digital pressure test can be used to confirm the existence of an

abscess. The damaged digit's distal volar aspect is gently compressed by the doctor. A bacterial infection is probably present if the area of blanching is bigger than expected.^[50] Clinical diagnosis include retronychia, onychomadesis, and Beau's lines. Examining the nail plate allows one to identify distinct nail modifications. One way to distinguish between onychomadesis and Beau's line is by looking for transverse depressions or nail plate shedding. Overlapping nail plate layers are a sign of retronychia. Patients should always be assessed for trauma, exposure to certain drugs, and recent history of serious illness. Up to two months before the first nail alterations, a review of viral diseases should be taken into account.^[51]

9. TREATMENT OF NAIL DISORDERS

Onychomycosis can be treated in a variety of ways, including nail removal, systemic therapy, combination therapy, and topical therapy. Relapse rates may be higher in patients over the age of 55.

9.1. Nail removal, avulsion

While removing an infected nail can be used as a treatment for onychomycosis, it is not the only option. Surgical avulsion of the nail Because diabetic individuals are more likely to develop gangrene, secondary infections, and poor wound healing, nail avulsion is frequently used to treat onychomycosis in these patients. Nevertheless, nail removal may be used in cases of severe stubbornness. Oral treatment, however, does not work.^[52]

9.2. Dermerits of surgical treatment

A surgical nail avulsion may cause the patient more pain than harm. Without further treatments, surgically separating the nail plate (fingernail or toenail) has no effect on the treatment of onychomycosis. This procedure should only be considered an adjuvant treatment used in conjunction with oral medication therapy.^[53]

9.3. Oral therapy

Systemic therapies for onychomycosis in the general population have been evaluated in several studies. The nail bed absorbs oral components through circulation, and it takes seven days for them to reach the local area to lower the imparting concentration (MIC) give up; the drug can be active in the nail for up to 90 days, and stopping the prescription doesn't require the nail to be totally clean. For almost 30 years, griseofulvin was the go-to oral treatment for onychomycosis. Nevertheless, it has a limited therapeutic window and significant adverse

effects. With a cure rate of less than 40%, it only works to combat dermatophytes and has several medication interactions. It is being used extensively to treat onychomycosis for a number of reasons. The imidazole class of drugs is effective against the majority of pathogens causing onychomycosis. Compared to Griseofulvin, ketoconazole has a somewhat greater intended effect, but it also has a number of adverse effects and medication interactions. Nowadays, it is frequently used to treat onychomycosis. It has been shown that fluconazole, 300 mg once weekly for six months, is safer and more effective. Triazole antifungal itraconazole reduces the likelihood of side effects by binding more specifically to fungus cytochrome P-450 than other azoles.^[54,55]

9.4. Nail lacquer

Human fingernails and toenails can be adorned and/or protected by applying nail lacquer or varnish. For many years, traditional nail lacquers have been used as cosmetics to preserve and adorn nails.^[56]

10. APPROACHES INVESTIGATED TO ENHANCE TRANSUNGUAL DELIVERY

Fig.12: Techniques of Nail Penetration Enhancement.

10.1. Mechanical methods

For many years, pediatricians and dermatologists have employed mechanical techniques

with differing degrees of success. They may cause discomfort and are intrusive.

1. Nail avulsion

Fig.13: Nail avulsion.

Under local anesthesia, total nail avulsion and partial nail avulsion are surgical techniques used to remove the entire nail plate or just a portion of the damaged nail plate. Salicylic acid and urea are examples of keratolytic chemicals that soften the nail plate in preparation for avulsion. Before topical therapy for onychomycosis, urea or urea and salicylic acid mixtures were used in clinical research for nonsurgical avulsion (chemical avulsion).^[57]

2. Nail abrasion

Fig.13: Nail abrasion.

To reduce the crucial fungal mass, sandpaper nail files are used for nail abrasion before antifungal nail lacquer treatment. Sanding the nail plate to thin it out or ruin it entirely is known as nail abrasion. You can use sandpaper numbers 150 or 180. A high-speed hand piece for sanding (350,000 rpm) is the tool utilized for this process. In order to facilitate the entry of topical medications, tiny holes have also been made in the nail plate using dental drills. By doing this, it could improve the antifungal nail lacquer's effectiveness. To get the best results, the process can be repeated.^[58]

10.2. Physical Methods

When delivering hydrophilic and macromolecular agents, physical permeation enhancement might be more effective than chemical techniques.

1. Carbon dioxide laser

Fig.14: Carbon dioxide laser.

Two methods were suggested so far

- a) Avulsion of the afflicted nail part is followed by laser therapy at 5000W/cm² (power density) in one technique. Direct laser treatment is therefore applied to the underlying tissue.
- b) The second technique uses a CO₂ laser beam to penetrate the nail plate. Daily topical antifungal therapy is administered using this technique, which involves puncturing holes created by lasers. The first approach is recommended.^[59]

2. Hydration and occlusion

Fig.15: Hydration and occlusion.

Diffusivity of water and other materials (i.e., drugs) increases as human skin becomes more hydrated; human stratum corneum retains up to ~300% of its weight in water; when stratum corneum is saturated, diffusivity also increases to several-folds; irritated nails are more elastic

and permeable; iontophoresis studies have used this property to further enhance penetration. Hydration may increase the pore size of nail matrix, enhancing transungual penetration.^[59]

3. Electroporation

In order to make the solute particles permeable through the lipid bilayers, electric transient aqueous pores are used.^[59]

Fig.16: Electroporation.

4. Laser ultraviolet light

One technique is to use UV light to heat the nail. The heat prevents fungus from growing beneath the nail plate.^[59]

Fig.17: Laser ultraviolet light.

5. Micro needle

Fig.18: Micro needle.

It is a system of improved delivery. With this technique, holes in the stratum corneum are

opened directly to the skin capillaries using arrangements of tiny needles. It also has the benefit of being too short to activate the pain fibers, which makes medication penetration easier.^[59]

6. Iontophoresis

Iontophoresis is the process of delivering a chemical across a membrane by applying an electric field. Clinical applications of the concept include cutaneous anesthesia, the treatment of hyperhidrosis, and antibiotics.

penetration as well as therapy for herpes simplex. Applications for iontophoresis are numerous and include transdermal, ophthalmic, dental, orthopedic, and more. Iontophoresis may improve drug diffusion through a nail's hydrated keratin.

Permeability/electroporation—electric field-induced pore induction; electroosmosis—convective solvent flow in pre-existing and newly created charged pathways; and electrorepulsion/electrophoresis—interaction between the electric field and the charge of the ionic permeant—are some of the factors that contribute to this enhancement.^[60]

Fig.19: Iontophoresis.

10.3. Chemical methods

Effect of penetration into the skin enhancers vary in different mammalian nails. Therefore, the following describes only a few compounds that were clearly able to improve medication penetration into the nail plate.

1. Keratolytic enhancers

The permeability of three imidazole antifungal medications (miconazole, ketoconazole, and itraconazole) was examined in relation to keratolytic agents such as papain, urea, and salicylic acid. Over the course of 60 days, it was found that no transungual antifungal

penetration was seen in the absence of keratolytic drugs. The spectrophotometric technique of analysis, which was not sensitive enough to quantify drug amounts reliably, further confirmed conclusions. The preliminary treatment with 20% salicylic acid (for 10 days) and the addition of 40% urea to the donor solution did not increase the penetration of these drugs. Nevertheless, pretreatment with 15% papain for one day and 20% salicylic acid for ten days improved antimycotic penetration.^[59]

2. N-acetyl-l-cysteine and mercaptan compounds

N-acetyl-l-cysteine and 2-mercaptoethanol increased the antifungal medication tolnaftate's permeability into nail samples. They proposed that these substances could be helpful in improving medication penetration through the nail plate in general. In vivo investigations have documented the penetration-enhancing capabilities of N-acetyl-l-cysteine with the antifungal medication oxiconazole.^[59]

3. -n-nonyl-1,3-dioxolane

2-n-nonyl-1,3-dioxolane (SEPA®) has been used to penetrate econazole (from a lacquer formulation) into the human nail. According to studies, compared to an equivalent lacquer without enhancer, Econazole penetrates the nail six times more efficiently in a lacquer containing 2-n- nonyl-1, 3-dioxolane. The "enhancer" group had considerably increased concentrations of econazole in the deep nail layer and nail bed compared to the control group. Additionally, the concentration of econazole in the deep nail layer of the "enhancer" was 14,000 times higher than the Minimum Inhibitory Concentration required to stop fungal growth.^[59]

11. FACTORS INFLUENCING TRANSPORT INTO THE NAIL PLATE

11.1. Molecular size of diffusing molecule

Penetration into the nail plate is inversely correlated with molecular size. Drug penetration decreases with increasing molecular size because it becomes more difficult for molecules to permeate through the keratin network.^[61]

11.2. Nature of vehicle used in formulation

Due to the nail plate is a hydrogel, water causes it to hydrate, which causes it to swell. Since the swelling increases the distance between the keratin fibers, the drug creates larger pores that allow the molecules that are permeating to diffuse, allowing for greater molecule permeation. It is consequently expected that medication penetration into the nail plate will be

decreased by substituting a nonpolar solvent for water, which does not hydrate the nail.^[62,63]

11.3. Hydrophobicity / lipophilicity of drug

The penetration of a range of homologous alcohols (C1–C12), diluted in saline, through avulsed human nail plates was investigated by Walters et al. The permeability coefficient decreased as the chain length increased from one carbon atom to eight carbon atoms, and then increased as the chain length climbed (>C12). According to the findings of the Walters et al. study, the nail plate is classified as a hydrophilic gel membrane.^[64]

11.4. PH of vehicle and solute charge

Weakly acidic or basic medications' ionization is influenced by the pH of aqueous formulations, which in turn impacts the drug's solubility and hydrophilicity/hydrophobicity. The pH of the vehicle also affects formulation solubility in the nail plate and how it interacts with the keratin matrix.^[65]

11.5. Degree of ionization

In general, ionic substances have a lower permeability coefficient across the nail plate than do their non-charged equivalents.^[66]

11.6. Nail plate hydration

One crucial element in determining medication penetration is the level of nail plate moisture. Delivery of the radio labeled medication was improved thrice when ketoconazole was able to penetrate excised human nails at varying relative humidity (RH) levels, ranging from 15% to 100%.^[66]

11.7. Presence of an intact dorsal layer

The biggest obstacle to medication penetration over the nail plate is overlapped cells. Drug permeability rises if this layer is partially or completely destroyed, for example, by removal of tissue, chemical etching with 30–40% phosphoric acid, or the application of keratinolytic enzymes.^[66]

11.8. Binding of the drug to keratin and other nail constituents

Considering keratin has been proposed to have a pH of about 5, it is positively and negatively charged at pH values lower and higher than this. As a result, depending on the charge of the molecules, it may bind or repel them. This might contribute to the decreased ionic compound permeability in nails.^[66]

11.9. Nail thickness and presence of disease

Drugs will have greater difficulty reaching to the nail bed if the nail is thicker.^[66]

CONCLUSION

Transungual drug delivery is influenced by various anatomical, physiological, and pathological factors. The unique structure of the nail, including its dense keratin composition, presents a barrier to drug penetration. Several approaches, such as chemical enhancers, physical techniques (e.g., iontophoresis, microneedles) have been developed to improve drug permeation. Treatment strategies depend on the type and severity of nail diseases, including onychomycosis, psoriasis, and dystrophies. Factors like hydration, pH, molecular size of the drug, and disease-induced nail alterations also affect penetration efficiency. Understanding these aspects is crucial for optimizing therapeutic outcomes in nail disorders.

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